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Review Article

REVIEW ON APPLICATIONS OF ICP-MS

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Abstract:

The main uses, working principles and applications of Inductively coupled plasma - tandem mass spectrometry (ICP-MS/MS) are reviewed in this article. The primary distinctions between ICP-MS and single quadrupole ICP-MS are explained, along with the resources available for technique development. To illustrate the capabilities of this innovative setup in the context of elemental, speciation, and isotopic analysis, real-world examples are provided. It has applications in a wide range of research domains, including the food, material, chemical, semiconductor, and nuclear industries, as well as the earth, environmental, biological, and forensic sciences. All kinds of samples and matrices introduced by a range of specialised equipment find a suitable atomizer and element ioniser in the high ion density and high temperature of a plasma. Prominent characteristics include maximum sensitivity (ppt–ppq), relative salt resistance, element response independent of compound, and optimal quantitation precision contribute to ICP - MS's unrivalled ability to effectively detect, identify, and consistently quantify trace elements. The molecular identification capabilities of ICP - MS hyphenated to species-specific separation techniques are expanded by the growing availability of pertinent reference compounds and good separation selectivity. ICP - MS is a productive and extremely sensitive technique for target-element oriented discoveries of relevant and unknown compounds, whereas molecular ion source MS is specialised in figuring out the structure of unknown molecules.

Keywords : ICP-MS, Applications, Principles, Sensitive, Characteristics.

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INTRODUCTION:

On June 6, 1978, the first mass spectra recorded with an Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer were observed. Working with visiting scientist Alan L. Gray, Robert Samuel Houk, a graduate student at Iowa State University in Velmer A. Fassel laboratory, established the foundation for the first publication on ICP - MS in 1980. Gray had already shown the advantages of elemental analysis using plasma-source MS, but using wall-stabilized DC plasma in argon [1-7]. Acknowledged as an excellent analytical method, ICP-MS has huge linear response, isotopic analysis capabilities, very low limit of detection (LOD), and multi-elemental capability. Furthermore, because the ICP ion source can handle both dry and wet aerosols and vapours, it is incredibly flexible to integrate with various techniques, including electrothermal vaporisation (ETV), direct injection nebulization (DIN), ultrasonic nebulization (USN), laser ablation (LA), and others, in addition to the typical sample input method of pneumatic nebulization. The response and capabilities of the ICP-MS technique can be significantly altered by the employment of a particular sample introduction system [8-14]. There has been a surge in interest in the application of ICP-MS, sometimes known as "Single Particle ICP-MS," for the measurement of nanoparticles and microparticles individually [15-19]. It has become one of the most advanced methods for elemental (ultra-)trace analysis of metals and metalloids in various matrices since its commercial introduction in 1983. Due to its special qualities, which include: (i) high sensitivity; (ii) multi-element capabilities; (iii) a broad linear range; and (iv) the ability to obtain isotopic information, a great deal of research has been published to date on its

applications in a variety of fields, including geochemistry, the environment, clinical and biological materials, food, and industry [20]. ICP-MS devices first struggled with spectral interferences since they were based on quadrupole-mass analysers, which had a limited mass resolution. Other advantages include high sensitivity, a pronounced multi-element character, a wide linear dynamic range, and the ability to obtain isotopic information. Many strategies, including (matrix-matched) blank subtraction, mathematical adjustment, cold plasma conditions, trace/matrix separation, different sample introduction techniques, and aerosol desolvation, have been proposed to deal with spectral overlap. While using one of these methods, or a combination of them, can yield accurate results for a variety of analyte elements and sample types, over the past 20 years, more straightforward and universal methods have been developed, such as quadrupole (Q)-based instruments with a collision/reaction cell (CRC) and high resolution sector-field (SF) ICP-MS instruments [21-27]. Over the last 15 years, a number of businesses have created quadrupole-based ICP - MS equipment that can be gas-pressurized and incorporate an additional quadrupole, hexapole, or octupole. Either (i) selective interaction of the analyte and/or interfering ion(s) with a reactive gas (e.g., H₂, O₂, NH₃) or (ii) collisions of the ions with a non-reactive gas (e.g., He), in combination with kinetic energy discrimination, can be used to remove interferences, depending on the kind of instrument. Use of isotope ratio analysis and interference-free quantitative assessment of metals and metalloids in various sample types using ICP-MS/MS [28-31].

Fig. 1. Flow chart representation on how to avoid spectral overlap using ICP – MS/MS [32].

ICP - MS INSTRUMENTATION

As of right now, the only available ICP – tandem mass spectrometers present in the market are Agilent 8800 (2012) and 8900 (2016). These devices are also known as Agilent Technologies triple quadrupole ICP-MS or ICP-QQQ units. As a result, this particular instrumentation must be cited when discussing the instrumental setup. The device resembles a conventional quadrupole system in that it has a quadrupole mass filter before it and an octo-pole reaction cell [32].

ICP-MS/MS is a flexible technology whose mass window of the first quadrupole can be adjusted from around 1 amu to entirely open, based on the challenges presented by each individual application. For the remainder of this review, the mode that use double mass selection will be called MS/MS mode, while the mode that uses a wider bandpass to operate the first quadrupole will be referred to as "open"/single quadrupole, or SQ mode. An overview of the many operation modes, scanning choices, and measuring techniques made possible by the tandem MS arrangement, as detailed in the next sections, is given in the table below [21,32].

Fig. 2. Pictorial representation of ICP – MS [83]

Table 1. Various operation modes are made accessible by Tandem MS configuration in ICP – MS [32]

	FIRST QUADRUPOLE (Q1)	SECOND QUADRUPOLE (Q2)
SQ Mode	Fully open (ion guide)	Fixed m/z ratio
MS/MS Mode	Fixed m/z ratio	Fixed m/z ratio
On-mass Approach	m/z Q1	m/z Q2 = m/z Q1
Mass-shift Approach	m/z Q1	m/z Q2 ≠ m/z Q1
Product Ion Scan	Fixed m/z ratio	Scan (2-260 amu)
Precursor Ion Scan	Scan (2-260 amu)	Fixed m/z ratio
Neutral Gain Scan	Scan (2-260 amu) m/z Q1	Scan (2-260 amu) m/z Q2 = m/z Q1 + $\Delta m/z^a$

^a $\Delta m/z$ is constant over the entire mass spectrum (2-260 amu).

1. Operational Modes : sq vs ms/ms :

There are 2 modes of operation for the ICP – MS : SQ and MS/MS. When the instrument is in SQ mode, Q1 can be utilised as an ion guide or as a bandpass mass filter. The analyte (m_1A^+), the interfering ions (m_1I^+) with the same m/z, and other contemporaneous ions (m_1C^+) with a different m/z all reach the CRC since Q1 is "fully open" in the first case. Using both Q1 and Q2 as real mass filters (1 amu bandpass), this approach selects a different m/z for the on-mass method or the

same m/z for the mass-shift method dependent on whether or not the analyte ion interacts with the reaction gas supplied. Because a certain m/z (that of the target ion, m_1A) is chosen in Q1, only the analyte ion and the interfering ions with the same m/z can reach the CRC in this MS/MS mode. Q1 effectively eliminates all concurrent ions with varying m/z (m_2C^+). This has several significant benefits, including (i) preventing undesired product ions from reactions between other ions and the reaction gas, (ii) lowering

non-spectral interferences or matrix effects that could affect the reactions taking place in the cell, and (iii) increasing the efficiency of the ion-molecule chemistry taking place in the cell [32].

2. Scanning Options [32]

In tandem mass spectrometry, certain scanning options enable the identification and tracking of precursor and/or product ions. These scanning choices can be viewed as potent instruments that offer a deeper understanding of the possibly intricate reactions occurring within the cell, hence assisting in the creation of interference-free measurement techniques. In this case, the MS/MS configuration of an ICP-tandem mass spectrometer allows for the use of product ion, precursor ion, and neutral mass gain/loss scans.

A. Product Ion Scan

The product ion scan in ICP-MS/MS is used to find the most appropriate reaction product ion formed following interaction between the initial analyte ion and the reaction gas within the cell in order to establish interference-free conditions with the greatest signal-to-background ratio. Q1 should be fixed at a given nominal m/z , usually the most abundant analyte ion (m^1A), but it can also be used to assess how a particular reaction gas affects a possibly interfering ion in order to do a product ion scan.

B. Precursor Ion Scan

Unlike a product ion scan, a precursor ion scan is used to learn more about the origins of a certain production. This is due to the possibility that the precursor ion scan, which results from a reaction between an as-yet-unidentified ion and the reaction gas (R) inside the cell, might obstruct interference-free identification of the analyte ion or a reaction product ion thereof.

C. Neutral Mass Gain/ Loss Scan

Neutral mass gain/loss scanning is another feature of tandem mass spectrometry. Rather of maintaining Q1 or Q2 stationary at a certain m/z , both quadrupoles are utilised in scanning mode, with a predetermined m/z differential between them. One can look for either gain or loss of mass, depending on whether the mass of the precursor ion is more or less than the mass of the corresponding product ion. In MS, neutral mass loss scans can be used to determine which molecular ions, when a precursor ion is broken by collision-induced dissociation (CID), lose a neutral fragment of a certain mass (e.g., H_2O) upon impact. However, as precursor ions in ICP-MS/MS are almost always lighter, the neutral mass gain scan is usually of more importance.

3. Abundance Sensitivity

Additionally, enhanced abundance sensitivity (AS) is offered by ICP-MS. AS is defined as the ratio of the maximum ion current measured at a given m/z value to the maximum ion current measured at a neighbouring boring m/z value ($m/z - 1$ or $m/z + 1$) for the same species [33]. When using a quadrupole mass spectrometer (QMS), the AS is in the order of 10^7 . This means the surrounding signals (at $m/z - 1$ and $m/z + 1$) contribute 1 count for a signal with 10^7 counts at a particular m/z . When the QMS was run at higher stability regions, there was a noticeable rise in AS. Furthermore, the addition of a nonreactive collision gas (He, for example) in the CRC may enhance the AS (10^8), but at the expense of a large reduction in sensitivity. The improvement can be attributed to the decrease in the kinetic energy distribution of the atomic ions. When determining ultra-trace amounts of an analyte element in a matrix containing extremely high amounts of the neighbouring element, or when determining extreme isotope ratios, where the nuclides taken into consideration exhibit a marked difference in abundance (e.g., $^{234}U/^{238}U$ or $^{236}U/^{238}U$), a spectral peak can have significant implications even though its contribution to the intensity at nearby or even farther away m/z values is very small [34-36].

OVERCOMING SPECTRAL OVERLAP: ON – MASS & MASS – SHIFT APPROACHES

Though the ideas of mass-shift and on-mass approaches—a means of avoiding spectrum overlap—have already been mentioned in passing in previous sections, it is vital to go over them in more detail before diving into the explanation of a few ICP-MS-based applications. The method chosen to get around the issue of spectral interference distinguishes the two. In the on-mass approach, also sometimes called direct determination, the m/z of the initial analyte ion of interest (m^1A) is the same for both Q1 and Q2. Anticipated is the reaction of the reaction gas (R) and interfering ion(s) (m^1I^+) to completely remove their contribution to the signal intensity measured at this m/z . While Q2 is being used to remove the newly created reaction product ion(s) (m^1ImRR^+), the target analyte ion is being monitored at its original m/z . The mass-shift technique, also known as indirect determination, in conventional ICP-CRC-QMS is frequently hindered by the absence of control over the ion-molecule chemistry taking place in the reaction cell [32,37].

MASS ANALYSER AND MULTIPLEXING CAPABILITIES

Ions are directed towards the detector by the mass analyser, which separates them based on their mass-to-charge ratio (m/z). Ions of a certain m/z can be detected at instrument-specific sampling frequencies

either quasi-simultaneously (time-of-flight instruments, multi-collector instruments) or sequentially (quadrupole and single collector instruments), depending on the kind of mass analyser. Short-lived transient signals are produced regardless of whether single cell analysis is carried out in bioimaging mode or in solution mode. More precisely, single droplets injected into the plasma cause transitory signals in the 300–500 μ s range, hence the study of suspensions requires instruments with an appropriate high time resolution. Consequently, multiplexing—the measurement of several elements in a single cell event—a primary goal of single-cell research is thwarted by the sequential detection of masses. Furthermore, even when detecting a single isotope, time-resolved observations of single cell events in solution mode are complicated by double or triple events due to the typical duty cycle of older ICP-QMS and ICP-SFMS (normal integration time of 1-5 ms). Therefore, the only ways to estimate the cell count objectively are with highly diluted cell (or nanoparticle) suspensions, which compromises throughput and detection limitations [38,39].

SINGLE CELL ANALYSIS IN SOLUTION

The measurement of single cells is subject to numerous technological and fundamental issues that are relevant to the objective measurement of single (nano)particles by ICP-MS (for further information, see a recent review in this journal). From a physical perspective, a de-solvated cell—one in which all water has been eliminated—shrinks down to the size of a particle. For this reason, single cell ICP-MS is subject to the same measurement artefacts as SP-ICP-MS, including unresolved double and multiple events, peak splitting, and signal loss due to dead-time during peak jumping. If the transport efficiency and sample absorption rate are known, the number of spikes detected over time can be used to estimate the number of cells in the suspension, much like with SP-ICP-MS. On the other hand, the peak intensity represents the entire quantity of a metal per cell [37,38].

SAMPLE INTRODUCTION

When measuring single cells in solution, the standard experimental configuration combines full consumption spray chambers with pneumatic nebulization. Conventional sample introduction systems typically have transport efficiency of 1% or less (removing droplets larger than 10 μ m) when a double pass spray chamber is utilised at a sample uptake rate of 1 mL min⁻¹. Cell transport efficiency can be greatly increased by lowering the sample absorption rate (to 0.01 mL min⁻¹), improving sample introduction designs, and using a sheath gas. Analytical figures of merit for sample introduction

systems have been evaluated elsewhere. Encapsulating the cells in fine droplets and transferring them into the ICP-MS is necessary for the introduction of whole cells into the plasma. Because most mammalian cells are between 8 and 30 μ m in diameter, they cannot be accommodated in traditional spray chambers. Several intriguing initial uses of V-groove nebulizers accepted relatively low transport efficiency once more. The creation of specialised high efficiency cell introduction systems (HECIS) was a significant advancement. A large-bore, high-performance concentric nebulizer was connected to a total consumption spray chamber in the arrangement. A sheath gas shielding the spray chamber walls from any contact with cells and a sample uptake rate of 0.010 mL min⁻¹ were critical requirements for increased transport efficiency. Once again, bigger mammalian cells were not compatible with this setup. Recently, mammalian cells with a 25% transport efficiency were added to the ICP without the requirement for further heating or make-up gas using a total consumption nebulizer and spray chamber. Another important factor in this instance was the low sample absorption rate of 0.010 mL min⁻¹. A unique pneumatic nebulizer with an on-axis low volume spray chamber is provided by the mass cytometry technical platform. It uses a heated make-up gas to evaporate the solvent from the droplets that are formed. The study revealed a 30% increase in transport efficiency when the sample absorption rate was 0.06 mL min⁻¹. Encasing cells in homogeneous microdroplets provides a useful substitute for introducing a sample of cells into a plasma [40-45].

CALIBRATION STRATEGIES AND TRANSPORT EFFICIENCY FOR SINGLE CELLS IN SUSPENSION [46,47,48]

Studies with quantitative data on cell suspensions are still in their infancy. Once more, single cell measurements were used to create calibration concepts and methods for determining the transport efficiency, which were originally developed in the field of nanoparticle analysis. The majority of research has focused on quantifying individual isotopes and examining the uptake of metals that are delivered exogenously through nanoparticles, platinum-based medications, or naturally occurring elements at the single cell level. Using inorganic standard solutions is one method for using ICP-MS to quantify metals in single cells in suspensions. For every calibration standard, the mass of every metal in each of these standards is shown against the count rate. Using the following equation, the mass of the element in the cell (mg) is determined.

$$mc = \eta \cdot Qs \cdot t \cdot (Ic - Ibg) / b$$

SAMPLE PREPARATION

For single-cell analysis, sample introduction methods greatly influence sample handling and preparation; this is significantly different for tissue samples and cell cultures. The sample preparation techniques used for the ICP-MS and LA-ICP-MS analysis of tissue samples and cell suspensions are the main topic of this paragraph [37].

APPLICATIONS

ICP-MS/MS is a relatively new technology. This section provides an overview of some of the applications that have been documented in the literature, emphasising the benefits that have been attained via the use of ICP-MS/MS while also highlighting the many methods and resources for method development that have been covered in earlier sections. In addition to quantitative elemental analysis, applications in the fields of isotopic analysis and hyphenated set-ups have been selected, where an ICP-MS is utilised in conjunction with other introduction methods, such as separation procedures. However, a large number of publications detailing both basic and more applied research using ICP-MS/MS have already been published in the worldwide literature and exhibit extremely encouraging outcomes. The objectives of this summary are to clearly and concisely highlight the current state and developments in the field of ICP-MS and to provide the reader with some references to specialised research papers. Based on the type of reaction gas employed, the applications have been separated into smaller sections to help organise this topic.

ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS

1. mono – elemental analysis

One of the most often utilised reaction gases in ICP-CRC-QMS is oxygen (O₂). Numerous elements exhibit reactivity towards O₂, with the most frequent ion-molecule reaction being O-atom transfer. Consequently, a target ion (A⁺) is converted into a reaction product ion (AO⁺) with a gain in m/z + 16. This reaction may be used to mass-shift or on-mass methods, depending on whether the reaction includes the analyte ion or the interfering ion. The applicability of O₂ in conventional ICP-QMS or in ICP-MS/MS operated in SQ mode may be limited by the formation of undesirable reaction product ions with the same m/z as the target analyte or the corresponding reaction product ion, and/or the presence of concomitant elements with the same m/z as the selected reaction product ion (in mass-shift approaches. Another illustration is the research done by Meyer et al, where As was identified as the matching AsO⁺ reaction product ion for the purpose of characterising As-containing hydro carbons (AsHCs) and assessing these

species' toxicity in both in vitro and in vivo investigations. Another element with significant spectrum overlap is sulphur (S), primarily due to O-based polyatomic interferences. The creation of SO⁺ product ions results from the interaction with O₂ [49-65].

2. multi – elemental analysis

Although it's common to view the specificity of some of the reactions occurring in the reaction cell as a benefit, multi-element techniques may find this to be a drawback. Multi-element determination is often regarded as one of ICP-MS's key advantages over alternative analytical methods. The word "during the same measurement" refers to simultaneous determination, which is particularly important when monitoring brief transient signals, aiming for high sample throughput, or dealing with restricted sample quantities. O₂ has been extensively utilised in ICP-MS/MS for the simultaneous measurement of several analyte components, typically utilising a combination of mass-shift and on-mass techniques within the same procedure [57,66-69].

ISOTOPIC ANALYSIS

It is commonly known that ICP-MS may offer isotopic as well as elemental information. Since at least two isotopes of the same element must be measured without interference for this kind of study, spectral interference may even have a greater impact on these isotope ratio measurements. Furthermore, a 1% bias in an elemental assay may not seem like much, but it significantly skews isotope ratio data beyond tolerable bounds. There have been studies published in the literature on the application of ICP-MS/MS for isotope dilution mass spectrometry (IDMS) and the identification of natural fluctuations in isotopic composition.

1. Isotope Dilution Mass Spectrometry

The potential of ICP-MS/MS for IDMS detection of S in organic matrices was evaluated by Balcaen et al, by monitoring the ions that arise from the SO⁺ reaction. However, the existence of interfering ions at the m/z of the intended reaction product ions (Ca⁺, Cr⁺, Ti⁺, and—in the event of an organic matrix—also ArC⁺) usually compromises accurate detection. To evaluate the potential of ICP-MS/MS, three different modes were used: bandpass mode, which emulates ICP-DRC-QMS settings; standard mode, which does not need gas; and MS/MS mode. It became clear that using the MS/MS mode with IDMS is the only method to obtain accurate results. As a proof-of-concept, S was successfully located in the NIST SRM 2773 (biodiesel) reference material. A general approach for correctly quantifying S in organic matrices was

provided using reverse phase HPLC-ICP-MS/MS [54,70].

2. Natural Variations in Isotopic Composition

High precision is needed in isotopic analysis to show the frequently minute natural fluctuations in isotopic compositions. Because of this, ICP-QMS application has frequently been limited to the investigation of induced changes in target element isotopic composition within the framework of IDMS or tracer investigations involving enriched stable isotopes. Also, while the ICP-tandem mass spectrometer is operating in the MS/MS mode, it may reject Sb^+ and Sn^+ ions by using Q1. By doing this, it is stopped that the CRC will react with N_2O to produce the interfering ions SbO^+ and SnO^+ . So, accurate isotope analysis of Cs became attainable, even with all of the initial difficulties brought about by different spectrum interferences. An additional usage of ICP-tandem mass spectrometry for isotopic analysis is the measurement of strontium (Sr) isotope ratios [61,71-73].

HYPHENATED ICP – MS APPLICATIONS

Similar to other ICP-MS instruments, an ICP-tandem MS can be enhanced for particular or more demanding applications by combining it with other sample introduction systems.

1. Chromatography

Structure-independent quantification is one benefit of the setup, but speciation analysis may be carried out with extremely sensitive detection when LC or GC is coupled to ICP MS. The benefit of employing tandem mass spectrometry in this situation is evident since several of the elements that are commonly of interest in speciation research (such as S, P, Cl, As, and Se) are prone to spectrum overlap in ICP-MS. The effluent of the LC system frequently contains a significant proportion of organic solvents, which might cause additional interferences in the ICP-MS detection and need to be addressed, especially when combining LC and ICP-MS. Blood plasma samples from a clinical research wherein human volunteers were given a pharmaceutical product containing the two target analytes were examined as a proof-of-concept. The assessment of the application of species specific double isotope dilution mass spectrometry (SSIDA) in HPLC ICP-MS/MS for protein-bound Se was conducted. To get around the significant spectrum overlap that affects Se isotopes, O-atom transfer (SeO^+ chosen as reaction result ion) was utilized. The effects of analyte losses and/or transformations during sample preparation and analysis were reduced by using this method. [74-79].

2. Asymmetric Flow Field – Flow Fractionation

Asymmetric flow field-flow fractionation to ICP-MS/MS (FFF-ICP-MS/MS) has been documented in the literature for the aim of studying and detecting nanoparticles. Menendez-Miranda et al. devised a technique for the interference-free measurement of Cd, S, Se, and Zn in order to assess the chemical makeup of Cd Se/ZnS quantum-dots populations (QDs). For this a multi-element approach was developed by combining on-mass and mass-shift approaches. It was shown that while O_2 is adequate to convert S^+ and Se^+ ions into the equivalent SO^+ and SeO^+ reaction product ions, Cd^+ and Zn^+ do not react with O_2 . Ti isotopes were identified as their matching $Ti(NH_3)_6^+$ reaction product ions, free from spectrum overlap. The approach developed was able to detect TiO_2 NPs in the size range of 75 to 400 nm in samples with relatively low salt concentration (e.g., lake water), even though the results were affected for samples with high ionic strength (e.g., sea water) due to aggregation/agglomeration with subsequent sedimentation. The examination of TiO_2 NPs and other oxide-based NPs in environmental samples is now possible thanks to these findings [32,80].

3. Laser Ablation

The principal advantage of the powerful combination of laser ablation (LA) and ICP-MS detection is the ability to examine solid materials immediately with little sample preparation and sample damage. Furthermore, by integrating LA with ICP-MS, the application range of ICP-MS is extended to encompass spatially resolved analysis of certain sample locations. As of right now, there aren't many LA-ICP-MS/MS publications in publication. This may be related to the transient signals that the LA unit may generate, but the double mass selection in ICP-MS/MS makes it seem like a somewhat slower detector than single quadrupole ICP-MS devices. Bishop et al. (year) used LA-ICP-MS/MS capabilities to evaluate the elemental bio-imaging (EBI) of trace metal distributions in tissue slices. Three different operating modes were assessed: bandpass (H_2 in the CRC), no gas, and MS/MS (O_2 in the CRC). The optimal circumstances were discovered when O_2 was utilized [80,81,82].

4. Development Of Metal – Based Drugs & Diagnostic Agents

Emphasis is placed on analytical techniques related to ICP-MS, which are especially suitable for measuring two metal(loid)-based cancer treatment drugs, improving our comprehension of the mechanism of action of antibiotic bismuth drugs and advancing the development of lead anticancer ruthenium compounds [32,37].

Table 2. Representation of few ICP – MS applications in a tabular form [84].

CASE STUDY	SAMPLE	ELEMENTS	REFERENCE
1) Brain diseases			
a. Parkinsons disease (6-OHDA model)	Mouse brain	Cu, Fe, Mn & Zn	Sussulini et al, 2012
b. Wilson's disease	Rat brain	Cu, Fe, Mn & Zn	Boaru et al,2014
c. Bipolar disorders	Human serum	Ca, Fe, Na, Mg, & Zn	Sussulini et al,2010
2) Contrast agents determination			
a. [Gd(DTPA)] ²⁻	Human articular cartilage	Ca, Cl, Cu, Gd, K, Na, Mg, P, S, Ti & Zn	Sussulini et al, 2013
b. Gd liposomal nanoparticles	Mouse tumour and kidney	Gd & Zn	Kamaly et al,2010
3) Anti cancer treatments			
a. Cisplatin & KP1339	Mouse liver, kidney, muscle & spleen	Pt & Ru	Egger et al,2014
b. Platinum	Human malignant pleural mesothelioma	Pt	Bonta et al, 2014
4) Other biomedical questions			
a. Cirrhosis & fibrosis	Human liver	Cd, Cu, Fe, Mn & Zn	M-M et al, 2013
b. Obstructive sleep apnea	Mouse brain	Co, Cu, Fe & Zn	Veasey et al, 2013

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